

International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA)- ERA Indexed

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<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/ijsea.html>

Scope & Topics

The International journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA) is a Bi-Monthly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Software Engineering & Applications. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Modern software engineering concepts & establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of software engineering & applications.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- The Software Process
- Software Engineering Practice
- Web Engineering
- Quality Management
- Managing Software Projects
- Advanced Topics in Software Engineering
- Multimedia and Visual Software Engineering
- Software Maintenance and Testing
- Languages and Formal Methods
- Web-based Education Systems and Learning Applications
- Software Engineering Decision Making
- Knowledge-based Systems and Formal Methods
- Search Engines and Information Retrieval

Paper Submission:

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ijseajournal@airccse.org . Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline** : July 14, 2018
- Notification : August 15, 2018
- Final Manuscript Due : August 23, 2018
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

For other details please visit <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/ijsea.html>

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